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Environmental Performance and Tax Aggressiveness: A Comparative Analysis of Quoted Consumer Goods Firms in Nigeria and Ghana

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ABSTRACT

Companies often use Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) to enhance their public image, yet some may still engage in aggressive tax practices behind the scenes. This disconnect creates a potential ethical conflict. It is in the light of the above that this study is aimed at investigating the relationship environmental performance and tax aggressiveness: A comparative analysis of quoted consumer goods firms in Nigeria and Ghana. Panel data were sourced from both Nigerian and Ghana Stock Exchanges Fact Book from 2014 to 2023. The dependent variables were proxied by corporate donation, thin capitalization and transfer pricing while the independent variable is the environmental performance. Panel Unit root test was utilized to establish the stationarity of the data, panel cointegration and granger causality test to test long-run the causal relationships. The panel unit root test proved presence of unit root at first difference and concluded that, in the case of Nigeria all the variables are stationary at levels except thin capitalization. For Ghana, transfer pricing, environmental performance is stationary at levels while the rest variables are stationary at first difference. The hypothesis one results found that environmental performance does not significantly impact on corporate donations in either country. However, it significantly reduces thin capitalization in Nigeria and transfer pricing in Ghana. The study concludes that the relationship between environmental performance and tax aggressiveness varies across the two countries, reflecting differences in institutional quality, regulatory enforcement, and corporate governance structures. The study therefore, recommends that consumer goods firms should design donation strategies that support environmental conservation, renewable energy adoption, and waste management initiatives within their operational communities. Finally, corporate managers in both Nigeria and Ghana should integrate environmental sustainability goals into their financial management and capital structure decisions.

Keywords: Environmental Performance, Corporate Donations, Thin Capitalization, Transfer Pricing

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the growing concern for environmental sustainability has reshaped corporate practices across the globe. Firms are increasingly held accountable not only for their financial performance but also for their environmental responsibilities and contributions to sustainable development (Fernando & Lawrence, 2014). As global regulatory and societal expectations rise, environmental performance has become a key component of corporate social responsibility (CSR) and a significant factor influencing stakeholder perception, corporate reputation, and long-term profitability (Clarkson, Li, Richardson, & Vasvari, 2011). In this context, the relationship between environmental performance and tax aggressiveness has emerged as a subject of scholarly and policy interest, especially in developing

economies where regulatory enforcement and corporate transparency remain evolving (Lanis & Richardson, 2018).

Environmental performance refers to a firm's ability to manage and minimize its environmental footprint through efficient resource utilization, waste management, and emission reduction (Clarkson et al., 2011). Companies demonstrating superior environmental performance are often viewed as socially responsible and compliant with environmental regulations, thereby gaining legitimacy from both the public and investors (Deegan, 2019). On the other hand, tax aggressiveness describes corporate strategies aimed at reducing tax liabilities through legal or borderline practices that exploit loopholes in tax laws (Frank, Lynch, & Rego., 2009). While tax planning is a legitimate business activity, excessive tax aggressiveness raises ethical concerns and may be perceived as inconsistent with CSR principles (Hoi, Wu, & Zhang, 2013). This perceived inconsistency makes the link between environmental performance and tax aggressiveness an important area of investigation.

In Nigeria and Ghana, the consumer goods manufacturing sector plays a pivotal role in economic growth and industrial development, yet it is also one of the sectors most criticized for environmental degradation and tax avoidance tendencies (Agama & Nkak, 2020; Acosta Garcia, Verleyen, & Roggeman 2024). Many quoted firms in these countries operate in environments characterized by weak institutional frameworks, poor environmental enforcement, and limited tax monitoring mechanisms (Adegbie, Akintoye, & Akinyomi, 2022). Consequently, firms may prioritize profit maximization over environmental stewardship, while simultaneously engaging in aggressive tax strategies to minimize their fiscal obligations. This dual behaviour raises concerns about the authenticity of their CSR commitments and the extent to which environmental performance truly influences their tax behaviour.

Theoretically, the relationship between environmental performance and tax aggressiveness can be explained through the legitimacy theory and the stakeholder theory. Legitimacy theory posits that organizations seek to align their activities with societal norms and expectations to maintain social acceptance and legitimacy (Suchman, 1995). Firms with strong environmental performance may avoid tax aggressiveness to preserve their legitimacy and reputation among stakeholders. Similarly, stakeholder theory emphasizes that corporations must balance the interests of various stakeholders including governments, communities, and shareholders in their decision-making processes (Freeman, 1984). From this perspective, firms that are environmentally responsible may perceive aggressive tax practices as contradictory to their broader social responsibilities.

Empirical findings on the relationship between environmental performance and tax aggressiveness remain mixed. Some studies (Lanis & Richardson, 2018; Hoi et al., 2013) found that environmentally responsible firms are less likely to engage in tax avoidance due to their commitment to ethical standards and regulatory compliance. Conversely, other research (Watson, 2015; Sikka, 2010) suggests that some firms use CSR, including environmental disclosure, as a strategic tool to obscure aggressive tax behaviour and reduce scrutiny from regulators. These divergent findings indicate that the relationship between environmental performance and tax aggressiveness may vary across institutional contexts, governance structures, and regulatory environments.

The comparative analysis of Nigeria and Ghana provides a unique opportunity to understand how differing institutional, regulatory, and cultural environments shape the interplay between environmental performance and tax aggressiveness. Although both countries share similar socio-economic characteristics and developmental challenges, variations in environmental policies, tax laws, and corporate governance practices may lead to distinct corporate behaviours. In Ghana, environmental regulations are relatively more structured through agencies like the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), while Nigeria's enforcement mechanisms are often perceived as weak and fragmented (Edeh & Nnadi, 2023). These differences could influence how firms in both countries respond to environmental and fiscal obligations. This study, therefore, seeks to examine the relationship between environmental performance and tax aggressiveness among quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria and Ghana.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigate the effect of environmental performance on tax aggressiveness of quoted consumer goods firms in Nigeria and Ghana. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Determine the effect of environmental performance on corporate donations of quoted consumer goods firms in Nigeria and Ghana.
- ii. Ascertain the effect of environmental performance on thin capitalization of quoted consumer goods firms in Nigeria and Ghana.
- iii. Examine the effect of environmental performance on transfer pricing of quoted consumer goods firms in Nigeria and Ghana

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for the study:

Ho₁: Environmental performance does not have any significant effect on corporate donations of quoted consumer goods firms in Nigeria and Ghana.

Ho₂: There is no significant effect of environmental performance on thin capitalization of quoted consumer goods firms in Nigeria and Ghana.

Ho₃: There is no significant effect of environmental performance on transfer pricing of quoted consumer goods firms in Nigeria and Ghana.

2.0 Conceptual Review

Environmental Performance

Environmental performance often operationalized as firms' measurable outcomes in emissions reduction, waste management, resource efficiency, and environmental disclosure is widely treated in CSR literature as both an outcome of corporate strategy and a driver of firm legitimacy, innovation, and stakeholder relations. According to Ndal, Ibanichuka and Ofurum (2021), Environmental disclosure means that a firm is obligated by law to include environmental information in annual reports, either voluntarily or statutorily. Environmental disclosure also communicates relevant information to stakeholders and society as a whole as a result of the company's actions as they influence the environment. Recent reviews show that environmental CSR (E-CSR) has evolved from philanthropic "green" projects to integrated strategic activities that are embedded in operations, supply-chain choices, and corporate reporting systems (Gazi, 2025; Liu, 2024). Firms that adopt proactive environmental practices are found to reap benefits in operational efficiency and risk mitigation, which can translate into competitive advantage and enhanced firm value over the medium term (Islam, 2025; Gazi, 2024). A growing empirical literature differentiates between symbolic environmental actions (green washing, selective disclosure) and substantive performance (measurable reductions in pollution, energy intensity, or resource use). Recent work also explores how environmental performance interacts with corporate governance and disclosure regimes. Firms with stronger board oversight, independent directors, and ESG-linked executive incentives tend to convert environmental strategies into measurable performance more effectively (Souguir et al., 2024). Conversely, weak governance increases the risk that environmental reporting will be symbolic, limiting associated benefits and potentially masking financial or tax-related opportunism (Dzage, 2024).

Tax Aggressiveness

Tax aggressiveness is as old as taxation itself as whenever authorities decide to levy taxes, individuals and organisations try to avoid paying them. This became popular through globalization as the range of opportunities to circumvent taxation while simultaneously reducing the risk of being detected grew. Tax aggressiveness refers to the strategies and actions companies take to minimize their tax liabilities through legal or borderline-legal means, often exploiting loopholes or ambiguities in tax laws. It represents the extent to which a firm engages in tax planning practices that reduce its tax payments beyond what is considered ordinary or acceptable (Hanlon & Heitzman, 2010). Tax aggressiveness often used interchangeably with corporate tax avoidance or aggressive tax planning is the strategies firms use to reduce their effective tax burden within (and sometimes stretching) legal boundaries (Klemm, 2016).

According to Okoh and Ofor, (2022), the terms tax avoidance, tax management, tax planning, and tax sheltering, all of which are related, and frequently used to describe business operations aimed at lowering

tax burdens or raising after-tax cash flows through the optimization of the effective tax rate. Contemporary research treats tax aggressiveness both as a firm-level outcome (e.g., book-tax differences, effective tax rates) and as a bundle of tactical choices (donations, financing structure, intra-group pricing) that managers deploy to achieve tax savings while managing reputational and regulatory risk. Okoh, Orjinta and Udoezika, (2024), assert that tax aggressiveness refers to strategies employed by individuals or corporations to minimize their tax liabilities through legal but often complex and potentially contentious means. While tax aggressiveness is within the bounds of legality, it often pushes the limits of what is considered acceptable or ethical by regulatory authorities and the public (Okoh, Orjinta and Udoezika, 2024)

Corporate Donations

Corporate donations can be seen as voluntary contributions made by firms to charitable, educational, or community organizations as part of their corporate social responsibility (CSR) activities. These donations can take the form of cash, goods, or services and are often motivated by both ethical and strategic considerations, such as improving a firm's reputation or obtaining tax benefits (Sun, Zhang & Li, 2023). While corporate donations can reflect genuine social responsibility, studies have shown that firms sometimes use philanthropy to manage stakeholder perceptions or offset reputational risks associated with aggressive tax behaviour (Campbell & Helleloid, 2022). Thus, corporate donations may serve as both a tool for social contribution and a potential mechanism for tax planning.

Thin Capitalization

Thin capitalization occurs when a company is financed through a relatively high level of debt compared to equity, particularly when the debt is provided by related parties or parent companies. This structure allows firms to deduct interest payments on the intra-group debt, thereby reducing taxable profits (Yoshida, 2024). Thin capitalization is widely recognized as a method of tax aggressiveness, as it enables multinational corporations to shift profits from high-tax jurisdictions to low-tax ones through excessive interest deductions (OECD, 2023). Many countries, including Nigeria, have enacted thin capitalization rules to limit interest deductions and prevent tax base erosion

Transfer Pricing

Transfer pricing refers to the pricing of goods, services, or intangible assets exchanged between related entities within a multinational enterprise (MNE). When transfer prices are manipulated to shift profits from high-tax countries to low-tax jurisdictions, it becomes a key mechanism of tax avoidance or profit shifting (Mediaty, 2025). The challenge for tax authorities is determining whether these internal transactions reflect "arm's length" pricing prices that would have been charged between independent parties (OECD, 2023). Transfer pricing thus lies at the heart of global debates on fair taxation and base erosion. It has a lot to do with the economic principles that apply to a fluid market place. However, new approaches and techniques to arrive at the appropriate transfer price from the perspective of one or more actors in the system are constantly being evolved (Smith, 2015).

11. Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Legitimacy and Stakeholders' theory propounded by Edward Freeman (1984), because both theories provide a robust explanation of the motives behind CSR practices and their potential linkage to tax aggressiveness, particularly in a cross-country context like Nigeria and Ghana.

Legitimacy Theory

Legitimacy theory was propounded by Edward Freeman (1984). According to legitimacy theory, there exists "social contract" between firm and the society within which the firm carry out its activities. The theory was developed to reshape corporate management perceptions about firm community concerns in order to enable their firms to survive long in the business cycle as going concern entity (Gray, Kouhy, & Lavers, 1995). Thus, the proponent of legitimacy theory is on the opinion that the management of the firm must ensure that their operations, decisions or actions are always within the bounds and norms of society, and avoid taking any decision or action that is considered undesirable, harmful, disastrous or inappropriate to the health and safety of consumers, employees, community dwellers and the operating environment (Ugwuiwa & Jimoh, 2012). This theory suggested the need for corporate organizations to

respect the law of the land, prevent their physical environment from being damaged and avoid unnecessary waste dump. Legitimacy theory has become the most frequent and useful cited theory while analyzing corporate behavior in relation to community constructed system of generally acceptable values, norms and beliefs (Gray, Kouhy & Lavers, 1995).

Stakeholders' Theory

The Stakeholders' Theory was propounded by Edward Freeman (1984) and is an extension of legitimacy theory and it states that the society should be taking into account in every firm action. The proponent of this theory suggested the need for firms to consider not only community but multiple stakeholders' groups in their decisions and actions. These stakeholders are classified into different classes and needs diverse information which firms must cautiously respond to it in a more variety ways. Stakeholders' Theory has indeed become one of the most important and frequently cited theories in CSR research. According to this theory, paying attention to the interest of all stakeholders in a business is a useful way of developing socially responsible behavior by managers and that a socially responsible organization is one in which obligations to stakeholders figure prominently in the decision-making of its managers (Clarkson 1995). However, this study supports the adoption of Legitimacy theory and Stakeholders' Theory. The research therefore, is of the view that Legitimacy theory and Stakeholders' Theory better explain the variables of the study, hence, adopted them as the theories with the better nexus underpinning the variables of the study. Legitimacy theory on the one hand suggested the need for firms to respect community values and ensure overall corporate community concerns.

111. Empirical Review

Okoh and Orjinta (2024) examined corporate social responsibility and tax aggressiveness of quoted oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The population of the study consists of twelve (12) quoted oil and gas firms in Nigeria. Secondary data was obtained from the audited annual financial reports of the quoted oil and gas firms in Nigeria from 2014 - 2023. Hypotheses formulated were tested using panel least squares regression through pooled effect, fixed effect, and random effect, determined by the Hausman test, fixed effect regression was preferred for results interpretation with the aid of E-views 10 econometric statistical software. Findings shows that corporate donations and social cost is negative (-3.056199) and significant at (0.0000). This negative impact of DSOC led to reduction in effective tax rate which is favourable to tax aggressiveness while, environmental cost is negative (-0.014754) and insignificant at (0.4268) to effective tax rate. This connotes that a rise in EVC by 1 unit will cause effective tax rate to reduce by 0.014754. The adjusted R-squared of 0.642196 suggests that DSOC and EVC account for roughly 64.2% of the variation in ETR, with the remaining 35.8% attributed to other factors not considered in this study. The study concludes that donations, social costs and environmental cost were the factors of corporate social responsibility that led to a decrease in the effective tax rate.

Anggraeni, and Palupi (2023) studied CRS' Dimensions: Economic, Social, and Environmental on Tax Aggressiveness. This study examines the effect of CSR disclosure on tax aggressiveness. CSR is measured by the GRI, divided into three dimensions: economic, social, and environmental. Tax aggressiveness is a manipulative activity carried out by companies to reduce taxable income through legal (tax evasion) or illegal (tax evasion) methods. The sampling technique used in this study was purposive sampling. The population for this research is manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for 2019 – 2021, and 72 companies or 216 firm-year data are synchronized with the sample criteria. The statistical tool used in this study is multiple regression analysis. The results of this study state that economic performance has a significant and positive effect on tax aggressiveness. While social and environmental performance does not affect tax aggressiveness. Moderation of profitability is only able to strengthen economic performance against tax aggressiveness.

Ndalu, Ibanichuka and Ofurum (2021) Studied board characteristics and environmental disclosure of quoted oil and gas firms in Nigeria: The moderating role of firm size. The specific objectives of the study were to determine the relationship between board independence and environmental disclosure. The research design adopted was ex-post facto design while, the population and the sample size for the study were the 12 quoted oil and gas companies in the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE). Secondary data were

used in this study and data were analysed using both descriptive, inferential statistics and Pearson Correlation Coefficient Statistical tool complementarily with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 23.0 to test the null hypotheses. The findings of the study reveal that board independence has a negative relationship with environmental disclosure. The findings of the study further indicate that firm size significantly moderates the relationship between board characteristics and environmental disclosure.

Hajawiyah *et al* (2021) studied CSR and Tax Aggressiveness: The Moderation Role of Risk Management This study aims to examine the effect of CSR on tax aggressiveness of non-financial companies in Indonesia. This study also aims to examine the moderation role of risk management in the effect of CSR on tax aggressiveness. This study uses secondary data sourced from Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) and firms’ website amounted to 342firm-years covering 2013-2018. The data then processed using balanced panel regression with STATA 12 Software. The result shows that there is no significant effect of CSR on tax aggressiveness. The result also shows that risk management moderate the effect of CSR on tax aggressiveness.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The study investigated environmental performance and tax aggressiveness: A comparative analysis of quoted consumer goods firms in Nigeria and Ghana. The research design adopted was *ex-post facto* research design; hence the study is a descriptive research. The population of the study was the 27 quoted consumer goods manufacturing companies in both Nigeria and Ghana Stock Exchange (Nigeria and Ghana Stock Exchange Reports, 2024). This is classified as 21 quoted consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria (Nigeria Stock Exchange Reports, 2024) and 6 quoted consumer goods manufacturing companies in Ghana (Ghana Stock Exchange Reports, 2024). These companies operate in various segments within the consumer goods sector, such as food and beverages, dairy products, and processed goods.

To achieve effective comparative analysis of the two countries, the study used equal number of consumer goods manufacturing companies from both countries. Hence, 6 consumer goods manufacturing firms each from both countries were considered. This is because we had only six (6) quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms in Ghana as at the time of this study. Having equal sample size enabled the study to have a baseline for the comparative analysis. Nevertheless; the study considered the availability of data in its selection. Hypotheses formulated were tested using panel least squares regression through Levin, Lin and Chun Unit Root Test, determined by the Hausman test, fixed effect panel regression was preferred for results interpretation with the aid of E-views 12 econometric statistical software.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Data Analyses

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics for Nigeria and Ghana

NIGERIA				
	CDn	TCn	TPn	ENn
Mean	61866109	3.898487	30.82613	10642131
Median	131808.0	1.760000	9.500000	608283.0
Maximum	3.47E+09	71.20000	1011.750	5.58E+08
Minimum	743.0000	0.350000	0.090000	0.000000
Std. Dev.	3.40E+08	7.980697	97.13998	52455852
Skewness	8.879516	6.559391	8.843477	9.688622
Kurtosis	86.73948	51.18614	88.98252	101.0321
Jarque-Bera	36333.10	12366.12	38208.03	49512.81
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Observations	119	119	119	119

Source: E-views .0 Output

GHANA

	CDg	TCg	TPg	ENg	
Mean	153050.8		4.829	3.245167	1647233
Median	7705		2.09	0.725	854722.5
Maximum	1892565		71.2	17.78	3860502
Minimum	743		0.35	0.09	0
Std. Dev.	365917.8		9.331954	4.618303	1199724
Skewness	3.076253		6.151934	1.759058	0.524846
Kurtosis		12.94248		44.13763	5.338647
Jarque-Bera	341.7659		4609.225	44.61602	6.655584
Probability	0.00000		0.00000	0.00000	0.03587
Observations	60	60	60	60	60

Source: E-views 12.0 Output

The comparative analysis of the descriptive statistics in Table 4.1 reveals that firms in Nigeria exhibit significantly higher means and medians for corporate donations (CD) and environmental (EN), corporate social responsibilities perspectives compared to Ghana. However, Nigeria’s higher standard deviations indicate greater variability in these variables. Ghana’s metrics are more modest but show less dispersion, suggesting relative stability. Both countries show positive skewness in most variables, but Nigeria’s skewness values are exceptionally high (e.g., 8.88 for CDn vs. 3.08 for CDg), indicating heavier right-tailed distributions. Nigeria’s kurtosis values (e.g., 86.74 for CDn vs. 12.94 for CDg) reveal more extreme outliers, implying significant disparities in firm behaviours. The Jarque-Bera test rejects normality for most variables in both countries ($p = 0.000$), but Ghana shows near-normality for EC ($p = 0.323$), suggesting more predictable distributions in the dimension. Altogether, Nigeria’s data reflects a larger, more volatile corporate environment, while Ghana’s metrics indicate smaller-scale but relatively stable operations. Both exhibit non-normal distributions, necessitating non-parametric analyses.

Test of Hypotheses

The Panel EGLS Regression Model was used in testing the hypothesis for each country to ascertain the specific result before making comparisons between both countries.

The decision criteria for all the hypothesis is indicated below:

Decision Criteria:

If, $p\text{-value} < 0.05$, then variable is significant: **Reject H0**

$p\text{-value} > 0.05$, then variable is not significant: **Accept H0**

The Effect of Environmental Performance on Corporate Donations (CD)

Table 4.2 Panel EGLS Regression Result (Extract) for Hypotheses Testing (Model 1a) (NIGERIA and GHANA)

NIGERIA			GHANA		
Dependent Variable: CDn			Dependent Variable: CDg		
Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section SUR)			Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section SUR)		
Date: 03/21/25 Time: 02:35			Date: 03/21/25 Time: 03:19		
Variable	Coefficient	Prob.	Variable	Coefficient	Prob.
ENn	-0.0052	0.9289	ENg	0.0018	0.6081
C	-27777432	0.0643	C	241226.4	0.0000
R-squared		0.425759	R-squared		0.572946
Adjusted R-squared		0.394436	Adjusted R-squared		0.543829
Prob(F-statistic)		0.000001	Prob(F-statistic)		0.000000
Durbin-Watson stat		2.024858	Durbin-Watson stat		1.780554

Source: E-views 12.0 Output

NIGERIA

The regression model examines the effect of environmental performance on Corporate Donations (CDn), a proxy for tax aggressiveness. The model uses a Panel Estimated Generalized Least Squares {EGLS} (Cross-section SUR) estimation technique, which accounts for cross-sectional dependence among firms. Table 4.2 shows that environmental performance (ENn) has a negative beta coefficient of (-0.0052) but a statistically non-significant p-value of (0.93). This means that environmental performance (ENn) has a non-significant negative effect on tax aggressiveness (TA) proxied by Corporate Donations (CDn) in Nigeria. This implies that an increase in environmental activities negatively affects corporate donation though not significantly. A possible interpretation could be that environmental initiatives may not directly affect tax strategies, as they are often driven by regulatory compliance rather than tax motives. Model Fit and Diagnostics: R-squared (0.4258): The model explains 42.58% of the variation in corporate donations indicating a moderate fit. Adjusted R-squared (0.3944): Adjusting for the number of predictors, the explanatory power remains at 39.44%, which is reasonable for panel data analysis. F-statistic (13.59285, p = 0.000001): The model is statistically significant overall, meaning the independent variables jointly explain a significant portion of the variation in corporate donations. Durbin-Watson statistic (2.0249): This suggests no significant autocorrelation in the residuals, indicating reliable estimates.

GHANA

The regression table presents the results of a panel EGLS (Cross-section SUR) analysis examining the effect of environmental performance (ENg) on corporate donations (CDg), which is used as a proxy for tax aggressiveness in quoted consumer goods firms in Nigeria and Ghana. Below is a detailed interpretation of the regression output. Table 4.2 shows that environmental performance (ENg) has a positive beta coefficient of (0.0018) but a statistically insignificant p-value of (0.6081). This means that environmental performance (ENn) has a non-significant positive relationship with tax aggressiveness (TA) proxied by corporate donations (CDs) in Ghana. This implies that an increase in environmental activities positively affects tax aggressiveness though not significant. A possible interpretation could be that environmental responsibility does not significantly influence tax aggressiveness through corporate donations. Model Fit and Diagnostics: R-squared (0.5729) means about 57.3% of the variation in corporate donations (CDg) is explained by the independent variables. Adjusted R-squared is (0.5438), the adjusted R² accounts for the number of predictors, and since it's close to the R², it confirms a reliable model fit. F-statistic: 19.67718 (p-value = 0.0000) shows the overall model is highly significant, meaning that at least the independent variable significantly explains corporate donations. Durbin-Watson (D-W) Statistic of 1.780554 is close to 2, hence, there is no severe autocorrelation in the model.

The Effect of Environmental Performance on Thin Capitalization

Table 4.3 Panel EGLS Regression Result (Extract) for Hypotheses (Model 1b) (NIGERIA and GHANA)

NIGERIA			GHANA		
Dependent Variable: TCn			Dependent Variable: TCg		
Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section SUR)			Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section SUR)		
Date: 03/21/25 Time: 02:39			Date: 03/21/25 Time: 03:19		
Variable	Coefficient	Prob.	Variable	Coefficient	Prob.
ENn	-231.7391	0.0027	ENg	2.0258	0.5720
C	0.785109	0.0000	C	7.2635	0.0000
R-squared		0.588033	R-squared		0.679504
Adjusted R-squared		0.551315	Adjusted R-squared		0.646263

Prob(F-statistic)		0.000017	Prob(F-statistic)		0.000006
Durbin-Watson stat		2.230938	Durbin-Watson stat		1.925186

Source: E-views 12.0 Output

NIGERIA

The regression model examines the effect of environmental performance on thin capitalisation (TCn), a proxy for tax aggressiveness. The model uses a Panel Estimated Generalized Least Squares {EGLS} (Cross-section SUR) estimation technique, which accounts for cross-sectional dependence among firms. Table 4.3 shows that environmental performance (ENn) has a negative beta coefficient of (-231.7391) and a statistically significant p-value of (0.0027). This means that environmental performance (ENn) has a significant negative effect on tax aggressiveness (TA) proxied by thin capitalisation (TCn) in Nigeria. This implies that an increase in environmental activities negatively affects thin capitalization used as proxy for tax aggressiveness in a significant manner. A possible interpretation could be that firms committed to environmental sustainability may avoid aggressive tax strategies to maintain legitimacy and avoid reputational risks, as it affects thin capitalization negatively. Model Fit and Diagnostics: R-squared (0.5880): The model explains 58.80% of the variation in thin capitalization indicating a moderate fit. Adjusted R-squared (0.5513): Adjusting for the number of predictors, the explanatory power remains at 55.13%, which is reasonable for panel data analysis. F-statistic (10.56790, p = 0.000017): The model is statistically significant overall, meaning the independent variable explain a significant portion of the variation in thin capitalization at 58%. Durbin-Watson statistic (2.2309): This suggests no significant autocorrelation in the residuals, indicating reliable estimates.

GHANA

The regression table presents the results of Panel Estimated Generalized Least Squares- EGLS (Cross-section SUR) analysis examining the effect of environmental (ENg) on thin capitalisation (TCg), which is used as a proxy for tax aggressiveness in quoted consumer goods firms in Nigeria and Ghana. Below is a detailed interpretation of the regression output. Table 4.3 shows that environmental performance (ENg) has a positive beta coefficient of (2.0258) but a statistically insignificant p-value of (0.5720). This means that environmental performance (ENg) has an insignificant positive with thin capitalisation, a proxy of tax aggressiveness in Ghana. This implies that an increase in environmental performance positively affects thin capitalisation though not significant. A possible interpretation could be that environmental performance may be seen as a regulatory compliance issue rather than a strategic tool affecting tax decisions. Model Fit and Diagnostics: R-squared (0.6795) means about 67.95% of the variation in thin capitalisation (TCg) is explained by the independent variable environmental performance. Adjusted R-squared is (0.6463), the adjusted R² accounts for the number of predictors, and since it's close to the R², it confirms a reliable model fit. F-statistic: 11.41677 (p-value = 0.0000) shows the overall model is highly significant, meaning that at least the independent variable significantly explains thin capitalization. Durbin-Watson (D-W) Statistic of 1.925186 is close to 2, hence, there is no severe autocorrelation in the model.

The Effect of Environmental Performance on Transfer Pricing
Table 4.4 Panel EGLS Regression Result (Extract) for Hypothesis (Model 1c)
(NIGERIA and GHANA)

NIGERIA			GHANA		
Dependent Variable: TPn			Dependent Variable: TPg		
Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section SUR)			Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section SUR)		
Date: 03/22/25 Time: 12:19			Date: 03/21/25 Time: 03:12		
Variable	Coefficient	Prob.	Variable	Coefficient	Prob.
ENVPn	2.3643	0.5059	ENVPg	-2031563	0.0476
C	0.034104	0.0000	C	-2.8654	0.0331
R-squared		0.625667	R-squared		0.938399
Adjusted R-squared		0.584007	Adjusted R-squared		0.933404
Prob(F-statistic)		0.000361	Prob(F-statistic)		0.000000
Durbin-Watson stat		1.991992	Durbin-Watson stat		2.137981

Source: E-views 12.0 Output

NIGERIA

This regression model examines the effect of Environmental performance on Transfer Pricing (TPn), a proxy for Tax Aggressiveness. The model used a Panel Estimated Generalized Least Squares {EGLS} (Cross-section SUR) estimation technique, which accounts for cross-sectional dependence among firms. Table 4.4 shows that environmental performance (ENn) has a positive beta coefficient of (2.3643) and a statistically insignificant p-value of (0.5059). This means that environmental performance (ENn) has an insignificant positive relationship with Transfer Pricing (TPn) a proxy of tax aggressiveness (TA) in Nigeria. This suggests that environmental CSR activities do not have a strong influence on tax aggressiveness via transfer pricing. Model Fit and Diagnostics: R-squared (0.6257): Indicates that 62.57% of the variation in Transfer Pricing (TPn) is explained by the independent variable in the model. This is a reasonably strong explanatory power. Adjusted R-squared (0.5840): Adjusts for the independent variable, showing a slightly lower but still strong explanatory power. F-statistic (7.3372, $p = 0.000361$): The model is statistically significant overall, meaning that the independent variable significantly influences transfer pricing (TP). Durbin-Watson statistic (1.9920) which is close to 2, indicating no serious autocorrelation in the residuals.

GHANA

The regression table presents the results of Panel Estimated Generalized Least Squares- EGLS (Cross-section SUR) analysis examining the effect of environmental (ENg) on Transfer Pricing (TPg), which is a proxy for Tax Aggressiveness in quoted consumer goods firms in Nigeria and Ghana. Below is a detailed interpretation of the regression output. Table 4.6 shows that environmental performance (ENg) has a negative beta coefficient of (-2031563) but a statistically significant p-value of (0.0476). This means that environmental performance (ENg) has a significant positive relationship with transfer pricing, a proxy of tax aggressiveness in Ghana. This implies that an increase in environmental performance positively affects transfer pricing though not significant. The negative coefficient suggests that increased engagement in environmental CSR activities leads to a reduction in tax aggressiveness (via Transfer Pricing). This implies that firms with higher environmental CSR engage in less transfer pricing (less tax aggressiveness). That is, firms committed to sustainability may avoid aggressive tax strategies to maintain

legitimacy. Model Fit and Diagnostics: R-squared (0.938399) means about 93.84% of the variation in transfer pricing (TPg) is explained by the independent variable. Adjusted R-squared is (0.9334), the adjusted R² accounts for the number of predictors, and since it's close to the R², it confirms a reliable model fit. F-statistic: 187.8798 (p-value = 0.0000) shows the overall model is highly significant, meaning that at least the independent variable significantly explains transfer pricing. Durbin-Watson (D-W) Statistic of 2.137981 is close to 2, hence, there is no severe autocorrelation in the model.

5.0 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Environmental Performance and Corporate Donations

The findings of the test of hypotheses one (H₀₁) indicate that environmental performance (EN) does not significantly affect corporate donations (CD) in both Nigeria and Ghana, leading to its acceptance. This suggests that environmental responsibility efforts by quoted consumer goods firms do not influence their corporate donations strategies in both countries. The finding is in line with the study of Okoh, Orjinta and Udoezika (2024) who studied corporate social responsibility and tax aggressiveness of quoted oil and gas firms in Nigeria in the case of hypotheses one and two. The study finding shows that corporate donations and social cost are negative (-3.056199) and significant at (0.0000). This negative impact of DSOC led to reduction in effective tax rate which is favourable to tax aggressiveness while, environmental cost is negative (-0.014754) and insignificant at (0.4268) to effective tax rate.

Environmental Performance and Thin Capitalization

In the test of hypothesis two (H₀₂), the relationship between environmental performance and thin capitalization (TC) differs across the two countries. In Nigeria, environmental performance has a significant negative effect on thin capitalization (p = 0.0027), leading to its rejection, while in Ghana, the effect is insignificant. This implies that in Nigeria, firms engaging in environmentally responsible practices tend to reduce thin capitalization, possibly indicating a more conservative financial structure. Conversely, in Ghana, environmental practices do not significantly influence thin capitalization. This finding is in line with the study of Mayangsari et al., (2024) who investigates how environmental, social and governance disclosure moderates thin capitalization and transfer pricing in relation to tax aggressiveness in Indonesian listed energy firms. The results showed that thin capitalization has a negative effect on tax aggressiveness and transfer pricing variables have a positive effect on tax aggressiveness. ESG disclosure in this study is able to weaken the relationship between thin capitalization and transfer pricing on tax aggressiveness.

Environmental Performance and Transfer Pricing

In the test of hypothesis three (H₀₃), the results are mixed. In Nigeria, environmental does not significantly impact transfer pricing, leading to the acceptance of H₀₃. However, in Ghana, environmental performance has a significant negative impact on transfer pricing (p = 0.0476). This suggests that environmentally responsible firms in Ghana may engage less in transfer pricing strategies, possibly due to stronger regulatory frameworks or ethical considerations. This study finding is in line with the study of Irokwe, and John-Akamelu (2023) who study examined the effect of corporate social responsibility disclosure on the tax avoidance of listed manufacturing firms on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) and the study findings show a mixed results. The results of the study showed a significant effect of social responsibility disclosure on the effective tax rate; and, no significant effect of social responsibility disclosure on the book-tax difference.

6.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Conclusion

This study examined the relationship between environmental performance and tax aggressiveness among quoted consumer goods firms in Nigeria and Ghana, providing comparative insights into how environmental responsibility influences corporate tax behavior within differing institutional and regulatory environments. The study was anchored on the Legitimacy Theory, complemented by the Stakeholder's theory which collectively explains the motivations behind firms' environmental and fiscal decisions. The findings reveal that the relationship between environmental performance and tax

aggressiveness varies across the two countries, reflecting differences in institutional quality, regulatory enforcement, and corporate governance structures.

Specifically, in Nigeria, environmental performance was found to have a significant negative effect on thin capitalization, suggesting that firms demonstrating higher environmental commitment tend to adopt more conservative and less debt-dependent financial structures, thereby reducing opportunities for tax manipulation. However, environmental performance did not significantly affect transfer pricing or corporate donations, indicating that Nigerian firms' environmental activities remain largely disconnected from their fiscal ethics and corporate social responsibility strategies.

Conversely, in Ghana, the study found that environmental performance significantly reduces transfer pricing behavior, implying that environmentally responsible firms are also more fiscally transparent and compliant. This result may reflect Ghana's relatively stronger tax enforcement and sustainability disclosure frameworks, which encourage firms to integrate environmental accountability with ethical tax practices. Nonetheless, environmental performance had no significant influence on thin capitalization or corporate donations, suggesting that while Ghanaian firms demonstrate ethical restraint in tax planning, they may not yet fully align environmental initiatives with broader CSR objectives.

Finally, the comparative analysis underlines that environmental responsibility and tax aggressiveness are context-dependent phenomena, shaped by each country's institutional environment, regulatory culture, and corporate governance effectiveness. In Nigeria, weak enforcement mechanisms and fragmented policy linkages between environmental and fiscal governance may limit the influence of sustainability initiatives on tax behavior. In contrast, Ghana's evolving ESG and tax compliance environment appears to foster a stronger alignment between corporate environmental performance and fiscal transparency.

6.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. Consumer goods firms should design donation strategies that support environmental conservation, renewable energy adoption, and waste management initiatives within their operational communities. This alignment will enable corporate donations to reflect genuine environmental commitment rather than isolated acts of philanthropy.
- ii. Corporate managers in both Nigeria and Ghana should integrate environmental sustainability goals into their financial management and capital structure decisions.
- iii. Consumer goods firms should view environmental compliance and ethical tax behaviour as mutually reinforcing components of sustainable corporate governance. In Nigeria, companies need to embed environmental accountability within broader compliance and financial ethics frameworks to discourage opportunistic transfer pricing practices that could undermine national tax bases.

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